

1 **Numerical upscaling of seismic signatures of poroelastic rocks containing mesoscopic**
2 **fluid-saturated voids**

3 **Yanbin He^{1,2}, J. Germán Rubino³, Santiago G. Solazzi², Nicolás D. Barbosa², Marco Favino²,**
4 **Tianning Chen¹, Jinghuai Gao⁴, Klaus Holliger²**

5 ¹School of Mechanical Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an, China,

6 ²Institute of Earth Sciences, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland,

7 ³CONICET, Centro Atómico Bariloche - CNEA, San Carlos de Bariloche, Argentina,

8 ⁴School of Information and Communications Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an,
9 China

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11 Corresponding author: J. Germán Rubino (german.rubino@cab.cnea.gov.ar)

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13 **Key Points:**

- 14 • We develop a numerical upscaling procedure to calculate seismic signatures based on a
15 novel coupled fluid-poroelastic model.
- 16 • In the presence of fluid-saturated mesoscopic voids, the newly proposed coupled approach
17 is more flexible and more accurate than existing methodologies.
- 18 • Application to a synthetic “vuggy” carbonate-type rock sample provides new insights into
19 seismic energy dissipation related to fluid pressure diffusion between micro- and meso-
20 scale pores.

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Abstract

We present a novel coupled fluid-poroelastic model and an associated numerical upscaling procedure to calculate seismic attenuation and velocity dispersion in porous rocks induced by fluid pressure diffusion (FPD) in the presence of mesoscopic fluid-saturated voids, such as, for example, vugs or fractures. By applying appropriate interface conditions, the proposed model couples the Navier-Stokes equations for viscous fluids with Biot's equations of poroelasticity to model the mesoscopic voids and the embedding background, respectively. A finite element method is employed to solve the coupled problem for a set of three relaxation tests, which enables us to compute the complex-valued and frequency-dependent equivalent stiffness matrix of the considered synthetic sample. The newly proposed fluid-poroelastic approach is compared with a purely poroelastic one as well as a fluid-elastic approach in a benchmark model containing interconnected mesoscopic fractures embedded in a poroelastic background. We obtain excellent agreement for the proposed approach and the purely poroelastic model by optimizing the material properties of the fractures for the latter, which demonstrates both the correctness and advantages of our method over the purely poroelastic approach for modeling fluid-saturated mesoscopic voids. We also observe that, while the coupled fluid-elastic approach and the proposed method provide consistent results with regard to seismic attenuation due to the fracture-to-fracture FPD, the latter also allows to account for the effects of fracture-to-background FPD. Finally, we employ the proposed methodology to explore the seismic characteristics of a synthetic "vuggy" carbonate-type sample, for which we visualize and interpret the resulting seismic attenuation in terms of FPD between the microscopic and mesoscopic pores.

43

Plain Language Summary

Seismic waves are commonly employed to study porous and/or fractured geological formations in the Earth's upper crust. In the presence of relatively small heterogeneities, such as fluid-saturated fractures or vugs, seismic waves may exhibit velocity variation and amplitude decay due to fluid pressure diffusion processes, which are important characteristics of seismic waves. To date, it remains difficult to understand how complex and fluid-saturated voids impact these seismic characteristics. To address this problem, we propose a novel coupled fluid-poroelastic model and develop a corresponding numerical upscaling procedure to calculate seismic characteristics of

52 porous media containing mesoscopic heterogeneities. Our results demonstrate that the proposed
53 approach is more accurate and flexible than previous related models, which, in turn, opens new
54 and interesting perspectives for the seismic exploration of corresponding geological environments.

55

56 **1 Introduction**

57 The remote detection and characterization of fluid-saturated features, such as, for example,
58 fractures and vugs, is of preeminent importance in many scenarios of applied and environmental
59 geophysics, including groundwater management and remediation, hydrocarbon exploration, and
60 geothermal energy production (e.g., Klimentos, 1995; Jha et al., 2007; Tester et al., 2007). Seismic
61 methods are widely recognized as being particularly effective and valuable in this regard (e.g., Liu
62 & Martinez, 2012). However, for rocks containing fluid inclusions in the mesoscopic scale range,
63 that is, larger than the typical pore and grain sizes but much smaller than the prevailing
64 wavelengths, the seismic resolution is generally insufficient to allow for direct imaging of such
65 features. Therefore, most related research efforts focus on analyses of particular attributes of
66 seismic data. Notably, seismic attenuation and velocity dispersion as well as corresponding
67 variations with the direction of wave propagation have been identified as diagnostic features that
68 may permit to estimate valuable properties of heterogeneous porous rocks, such as, for example,
69 fluid saturation, fracture orientations, and fracture compliances (e.g., Liu et al., 2007; Müller et al.,
70 2010; Schijns et al., 2012).

71

72 In the presence of fluid-filled pores and/or voids, a passing seismic wave causes fluid pressure
73 gradients and, thus, dissipates energy due to viscous friction. This mechanism of seismic
74 attenuation is generally referred to as wave-induced fluid flow (WIFF) or fluid pressure diffusion
75 (FPD). White (1975) first proposed this mechanism at the mesoscopic scale and Dutta & Ode
76 (1979a, 1979b) subsequently framed it in the context of Biot's (1941, 1962) theory of
77 poroelasticity. Pride et al. (2004) developed a double-porosity model to include the effect of
78 mesoscopic fluid inclusions on the basis of Biot's (1941, 1962) theory. Ba et al. (2011) also
79 presented the so-called Biot-Rayleigh theory for double-porosity media, which provides
80 qualitatively similar seismic attenuation of fast compressional wave with that of Pride's model

81 (2004) but allows to calculate additionally the velocity and attenuation of two slow compressional
82 waves. More recently, Fu et al. (2018, 2020) derived numerical solutions to quantify seismic
83 dispersion and attenuation as well as semi-analytical solutions to assess frequency-dependent
84 velocity anisotropy of porous rocks in the presence of a sparse distribution of aligned slit cracks.
85 Due to inherent limitations of the above analytical solutions, accurate numerical schemes for
86 calculating seismic signatures in porous rocks with mesoscopic-scale heterogeneities are needed,
87 for example, for heterogeneities with complex geometries and/or spatial distributions. Although
88 many numerical schemes have been developed to solve the poroelastic wave equations in
89 heterogeneous media, they become computationally inefficient when used to calculate seismic
90 attenuation due to WIFF. This is due to the fact that seismic wave propagation and wave-induced
91 FPD prevail at significantly different spatial scales. Correspondingly, numerical upscaling
92 techniques based on creep and/or relaxation tests are currently the most efficient approaches to
93 quantify the corresponding FPD effects (Masson & Pride, 2007; Rubino et al., 2009; Wenzlau et
94 al., 2010; Quintal et al., 2011).

95

96 Numerical upscaling approaches for assessing the seismic response of heterogeneous porous rocks
97 are commonly based on Biot's (1941, 1962) equations, where mesoscopic heterogeneities are
98 represented as poroelastic features with different hydraulic and mechanical properties compared
99 to the embedding porous background (e.g., Brajanovski et al., 2005; Rubino et al., 2013, 2014).
100 Masson and Pride (2007) proposed a quasi-static creep test to estimate seismic attenuation induced
101 by FPD with a finite difference algorithm. Rubino et al. (2009) presented a related numerical
102 upscaling procedure to calculate equivalent seismic signatures of heterogeneous fluid-saturated
103 porous media based on a frequency-domain finite element method. Wenzlau et al. (2010) and
104 Carcione et al. (2011) performed numerical relaxation experiments based on the poroelastic
105 equations to estimate equivalent seismic characteristics in the presence of effective vertical
106 transverse isotropy (VTI). Quintal et al. (2011) solved the so-called u - p form of Biot's (1941)
107 consolidation equations to upscale seismic signatures of poroelastic rocks with mesoscopic
108 heterogeneities. Masson and Pride (2014) extended their original isotropic methodology (Masson
109 & Pride, 2007) to orthotropic materials. The common aspect shared by all these works is that they
110 are designed for isotropic or specific anisotropic systems of relatively high symmetry. To
111 overcome this limitation, Rubino et al. (2016) developed a fully generalized numerical upscaling

112 procedure that allows for computing equivalent seismic signatures in the presence of arbitrary
113 effective anisotropy.

114

115 Although the Biot-based upscaling procedures mentioned above facilitate the study of the effects
116 of FPD on seismic signatures (e.g., Rubino et al., 2013, 2014, 2017; Hunziker et al., 2018; Solazzi
117 et al., 2020), they are only effective as long as the considered mesoscopic heterogeneities can be
118 represented as porous features. However, in some scenarios, such as in the presence of vugs and
119 open fractures, the mesoscopic heterogeneities effectively correspond to fluid-saturated voids,
120 which, in turn, defies their representation as parts of a poroelastic continuum. While attempts have
121 been made to model mesoscopic voids as fluid-saturated inclusions (e.g., Chapman, 2003, Hudson,
122 1981, Quintal, 2016, 2019), the common limitation of these approaches is that they do not allow
123 for a comprehensive quantification of FPD effects. For example, corresponding analytical
124 characterizations (e.g., Hudson, 1981; Chapman, 2003) assume simplified geometries of fluid
125 inclusions and, hence, their applicability is restricted to idealized geometries and they cannot
126 properly account for interactions between fluid inclusions (Lissa et al., 2019). On the other hand,
127 current numerical approaches dealing with fluid-saturated voids (Quintal et al., 2016, 2019) cannot
128 adequately describe the multiplicity of scales associated with FPD effects because the background
129 is modeled as an elastic solid. Vinci et al. (2014b) studied seismic attenuation associated with flow
130 in fractures based on a hybrid upscaling approach (Vinci et al., 2014a), where the background
131 medium is characterized by Biot's (1941) quasi-static poroelastic equations, while the dynamic
132 aspect related to fluid flow within the fractures is approximated by a 1D solution of the Navier-
133 Stokes (NS) equations in the laminar regime. Due to the assumption of axial symmetry and the use
134 of the cubic law for the approximation of the fluid flow in fractures, the applicability of this
135 approach is, however, limited to idealized and simplistic scenarios. For example, it is neither
136 applicable to fracture surfaces with asperities and/or contact areas nor to multiple intersecting
137 fractures.

138

139 To overcome these limitations, we propose a novel upscaling framework, in which the mesoscopic
140 fluid-saturated voids are represented by the linearized quasi-static NS equations (Landau &
141 Lifshitz, 1959), while the embedding poroelastic background is described by the Biot's (1941)

142 consolidation equations. The two systems of equations are coupled using appropriate interface
 143 conditions. The numerical upscaling procedure is then implemented by solving the coupled
 144 problem with a finite element method for three oscillatory relaxation tests applied to a
 145 representative elementary volume (REV) of the heterogeneous formation of interest. The spatially
 146 averaged responses of the probed REV enable us to determine the components of an effective
 147 frequency-dependent and complex-valued symmetric stiffness matrix through a least-squares
 148 procedure (Rubino et al., 2016), which, in turn, permits to obtain the anisotropic seismic response
 149 of the formation of interest. An important advantage of the proposed approach is that, while being
 150 more flexible with respect to the representation of mesoscopic fluid-saturated voids than current
 151 methods, it also permits to quantify the associated FPD effects without the need to replace the fluid
 152 inclusions with equivalent media. Moreover, this novel methodology enables us to assess in which
 153 scenarios a purely poroelastic representation is appropriate for estimating seismic signatures of
 154 porous media containing mesoscopic fluid inclusions. We validate the proposed approach by first
 155 making a comprehensive comparison with pertinent benchmark models of fractured samples
 156 before considering a more realistic synthetic vuggy carbonate-type model, where we analyze the
 157 seismic attenuation due to fluid pressure communication between the prevailing mesoscopic and
 158 microscopic pores.

159 **2 Methodology**

160 Figure 1a illustrates the concept of seismic wave propagation in a heterogeneous porous
 161 environment, which locally may contain fluid filled voids, such as, for example, fractures, vuggy
 162 pores, and karstic dissolution features. To determine the dynamic properties of the probed porous
 163 medium, we consider REV's of the formations of interest (Figure 1b). Figure 1c illustrates a
 164 canonical example of a fluid inclusion Ω_f embedded in a poroelastic domain Ω_p . To model the
 165 response of the heterogeneous medium under harmonic deformation, we consider Biot's (1941)
 166 consolidation equations and the linearized NS equations (Landau & Lifshitz, 1959; Quintal et al.,
 167 2016) to describe the behavior of the poroelastic background and the fluid inclusion, respectively.
 168 The two domains are coupled by imposing suitable conditions along the interface Γ_{pf} . Several
 169 oscillatory relaxation tests are carried out under appropriate boundary conditions (BCs) along
 170 external edges of the REV. This enables us to calculate the harmonic response of the coupled
 171 system in term of, for example, the averaged stresses and strains, the fluid pressure distribution as

172 well as the local energy dissipation. Assuming that the probed poroelastic environment containing
 173 mesoscopic fluid inclusions can be approximated by a homogeneous anisotropic viscoelastic
 174 medium at the wavelength scale, we can estimate the complex-valued and frequency-dependent
 175 stiffness matrix of the equivalent viscoelastic medium using the averaged stresses and strains
 176 (Rubino et al., 2016). Finally, we solve the corresponding viscoelastic wave equations to calculate
 177 the effective phase velocities and inverse quality factors as functions of frequency and direction of
 178 propagation. In the following, we introduce the mathematical description of the proposed
 179 methodology.

180
 181 Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the problem considered in this study. (a) Seismic wave
 182 propagation in heterogeneous porous environment containing fluid-filled voids. (b) Conceptual
 183 representation of two typical types of such fluid inclusions (green color) embedded in a porous
 184 background (gray color). Top: carbonate-type vuggy mesopores (modified from Anselmetti et al.,
 185 1998); bottom: fracture network in a porous medium (modified from Montemagno & Pyrak-Nolte,
 186 1995). (c) Sketch of fluid-filled void Ω_f embedded in a porous background Ω_p .

187 2.1 Coupled System of NS-Biot Equations

188 When a seismic wave propagates through porous rocks containing mesoscopic fluid inclusions, it
 189 experiences attenuation and velocity dispersion in response to energy dissipation. In the context of
 190 this work, the dominant physical process of interest is FPD and, hence, inertial effects can
 191 generally be neglected (Rubino et al., 2016). In the following, we outline a new model to
 192 adequately describe this phenomenon in the presence of mesoscopic fluid-filled voids, which uses

193 the Biot's (1941) consolidation equations to describe the porous background and the linearized
 194 quasi-static NS equations to characterize the fluid inclusions.

195

196 In the poroelastic domain Ω_p , Biot's (1941) consolidation equations in the frequency-space
 197 domain respond to

$$198 \quad -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$199 \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T}_f = j\omega \frac{\eta}{\kappa} \mathbf{w}, \quad (2)$$

200 where we use the sign convention for which the time derivative operator is equal to the factor
 201 “ $+j\omega$ ” in the frequency domain, with j denoting the imaginary unit, $\omega = 2\pi f$ the angular
 202 frequency, and f the frequency; η is the dynamic viscosity of the pore fluid, κ the permeability,
 203 and \mathbf{w} the displacement vector of the pore fluid relative to the solid skeleton. For small
 204 deformations of the porous medium in response to passing seismic waves, we can use the linear
 205 approximation $\mathbf{w} = \phi(\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{u})$ (Biot, 1962), where ϕ denotes the porosity, and \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{u} are the
 206 absolute displacement vectors of the particles of the pore fluid and the solid matrix, respectively.
 207 The total stress tensor \mathbf{T} and the pore fluid stress \mathbf{T}_f in the porous medium can be expressed as
 208 (Biot, 1941)

$$209 \quad \mathbf{T} = \left[\left(K_b - \frac{2}{3}\mu_b + \alpha^2 M \right) \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} - \alpha M \zeta \right] \mathbf{I} + 2\mu_b \mathbf{E}, \quad (3)$$

$$210 \quad \mathbf{T}_f = M(\alpha \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} - \zeta) \mathbf{I}, \quad (4)$$

211 where \mathbf{I} is the identity tensor, $\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2}[\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T]$ the second-order elastic strain tensor, $\zeta = -\nabla \cdot$
 212 \mathbf{w} a measure of the local change in the fluid content, μ_b the shear modulus of the poroelastic
 213 medium, and K_b the bulk modulus of the dry porous matrix. Recall that $\mathbf{T}_f = -P_f \mathbf{I}$, with P_f
 214 denoting the pressure of the pore fluid. The Biot-Willis constant α and the fluid storage coefficient
 215 M are defined as

$$216 \quad \alpha = 1 - \frac{K_b}{K_s}, \quad (5)$$

$$217 \quad \frac{1}{M} = \frac{\alpha - \phi}{K_s} + \frac{\phi}{K_f}, \quad (6)$$

218 where K_s and K_f are the bulk moduli of the solid grains and the pore fluid, respectively.

219

220 In the fluid domain Ω_f , we assume that the frequencies of seismically induced fluid displacements
 221 are sufficiently low so that we can ignore acceleration terms as well as the bulk viscosity of the
 222 fluid. Thus, we consider the linearized quasi-static NS equations (Landau & Lifshitz, 1959; Quintal
 223 et al., 2016)

$$224 \quad \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}^f = 0, \quad (7)$$

225 where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^f$ is the stress tensor of the fluid in Ω_f . The constitutive relation of the fluid, accounting
 226 for the viscosity and compressibility, responds to (Landau & Lifshitz, 1959; Quintal et al., 2016)

$$227 \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}^f = -p\mathbf{I} - \frac{2}{3}j\omega\eta(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^f)\mathbf{I} + 2j\omega\eta\mathbf{E}^f, \quad (8)$$

228 where the vector \mathbf{u}^f denotes the displacement of the fluid, $\mathbf{E}^f = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla\mathbf{u}^f + (\nabla\mathbf{u}^f)^T)$ is the strain
 229 tensor, p is the in-situ pressure of the fluid, which can be explicitly expressed in terms of the fluid
 230 displacement vector as

$$231 \quad p = -K_f\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^f. \quad (9)$$

232 Equations (7) to (9) can be used to describe the laminar flow behavior of a Newtonian fluid. By
 233 substituting equations (8) and (9) into equation (7), one can obtain a more compact form of NS
 234 equations expressed in terms of fluid displacement variables only. This displacement form of NS
 235 equations will be used for the numerical implementation because of its inherent computational
 236 efficiency.

237

238 Considering the interaction between the fluid inclusions and the embedding porous background,
 239 coupling between the fluid domain Ω_f and the poroelastic domain Ω_p can be achieved by imposing
 240 the following interface conditions along Γ_{pf} :

241 1) Requiring mass conservation implies (Ager et al., 2019a, 2019b)

$$242 \quad \mathbf{u}^f \cdot \mathbf{n}_f = (\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{w}) \cdot \mathbf{n}_f, \quad (10)$$

243 where \mathbf{n}_f is an outward-directed unit vector normal to the fluid boundary.

244

245 2) Assuming that there is no-slip between the porous background and the fluid inclusions, this
 246 can be expressed as (Ager et al., 2019a, 2019b)

$$247 \quad [\mathbf{u}^f - (\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{w})] \cdot \mathbf{t}_f = 0, \quad (11)$$

248 where \mathbf{t}_f is the tangential unit vector on the fluid boundary. Please notice that other conditions are
 249 conceivable to allow for more detailed descriptions of relative motion between fluid inclusions
 250 and a poroelastic background. For example, Beavers & Joseph (1967) pointed out that a fluid in
 251 contact with a porous medium tends to flow faster at the interface than in the porous medium. This
 252 particular behavior is related with the fact that the interface separating the two media is difficult
 253 to define, and the porous system is a mixture of fluid and solid grains (Badia et al., 2009). The
 254 impact of these additional complexities will be explored in future works.

255
 256 3) Requiring that the stress of the porous medium is balanced by the stress of the fluid (Ager et
 257 al., 2019a, 2019b)

$$258 \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}^f \cdot \mathbf{n}_f = -\mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{n}_p, \quad (12)$$

259 where \mathbf{n}_p is an outward-directed unit vector normal to the poroelastic boundary. At the coupling
 260 interface Γ_{pf} , it is noted that $\mathbf{n}_f = -\mathbf{n}_p$.

261
 262 4) Normal component of stress applied by the fluid being balanced by pressure of pore fluid
 263 implies (Ager et al., 2019a, 2019b)

$$264 \quad \mathbf{n}_f \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^f \cdot \mathbf{n}_f) = -P_f \equiv \mathbf{n}_p \cdot (\mathbf{T}_f \cdot \mathbf{n}_p). \quad (13)$$

265 Equations (1) to (9), together with the coupling conditions (10) to (13), fully describe the physical
 266 behavior of the considered poroelastic samples containing mesoscopic-scale fluid inclusions.

267
 268 Equations (10) to (13) describe the coupling between a fluid and a porous medium. As in our work
 269 the behavior of the latter is governed by Biot's theory, which cannot explicitly handle microscopic
 270 features, potential microscopic details of the interface should be neglected when using equations
 271 (10) to (13). This scale limitation of the interface conditions is similar to that mentioned by
 272 Gurevich & Schoenberg (1999) when deriving conditions for an interface separating two fluid-
 273 saturated porous media. In addition, the interface conditions describe an open-pore scenario, that

274 is, we assume that the inclusions and the porous background are hydraulically connected. In
 275 practice, scenarios involving partially connected or fully sealed interfaces are also conceivable, as,
 276 for example, clays or fines may clog the pores in the vicinity of the interfaces between the fluid
 277 inclusions and the poroelastic background (Gurevich & Schoenberg, 1999). In future works, we
 278 will consider the partially open and sealed interface cases and analyze the effects of interface
 279 hydraulic connectivity on the seismic signatures.

280 2.2 Oscillatory Relaxation Tests

281 Mesoscale fluid inclusions often exhibit complicated geometries, orientations, and distributions.
 282 As a result, seismic signatures, such as phase velocity and attenuation, usually show anisotropic
 283 characteristics. Following Rubino et al. (2016), we apply two compressive oscillatory relaxation
 284 tests and one shear relaxation test on a corresponding REV in order to calculate the effective
 285 anisotropic response of a 2D medium of interest. For each test, boundary conditions, similar to
 286 those provided by Rubino et al. (2016), are assigned at the outer edges of the REV (Figure 1c).
 287 While, due to the immense computational cost of 3D simulations, we limit the current study to 2D,
 288 it is important to note that the extension of the proposed methodology to 3D is conceptually
 289 straightforward. The governing equations (1) to (13) would remain the same and, for the upscaling
 290 procedure, one can follow the 3D generalization presented by Jian et al. (2021) for poroelastic
 291 media.

292
 293 For mathematical simplicity, we define the corresponding outer boundaries of a rectangular REV
 294 as $\Gamma = \Gamma_T \cup \Gamma_B \cup \Gamma_L \cup \Gamma_R$, where Γ_T , Γ_B , Γ_L and Γ_R refer to the top, bottom, left, and right
 295 boundaries, respectively. The three tests and corresponding BCs used are summarized as follows.

- 296 ● Compressive oscillatory relaxation test in vertical direction. This is achieved by imposing
 297 the following BCs:

$$298 \quad \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}_p = -\Delta u, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma_T \cup \Gamma_B, \quad (14)$$

$$299 \quad \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}_p = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma_L \cup \Gamma_R, \quad (15)$$

$$300 \quad (\mathbf{T}\mathbf{n}_p) \cdot \mathbf{t}_p = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma, \quad (16)$$

$$301 \quad \mathbf{w} = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma, \quad (17)$$

302 where \mathbf{t}_p is the unit tangent on Γ .

- 303 ● Compressive oscillatory relaxation test in horizontal direction. This is achieved by
 304 imposing the following BCs:

$$305 \quad \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}_p = -\Delta u, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma_L \cup \Gamma_R, \quad (18)$$

$$306 \quad \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}_p = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma_T \cup \Gamma_B, \quad (19)$$

$$307 \quad (\mathbf{T}\mathbf{n}_p) \cdot \mathbf{t}_p = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma, \quad (20)$$

$$308 \quad \mathbf{w} = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma. \quad (21)$$

- 309 ● Shear oscillatory relaxation test. This is achieved by imposing the following BCs:

$$310 \quad \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{t}_p = \Delta u, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma_T \cup \Gamma_B, \quad (22)$$

$$311 \quad \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{t}_p = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma_L \cup \Gamma_R, \quad (23)$$

$$312 \quad (\mathbf{T}\mathbf{n}_p) \cdot \mathbf{n}_p = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma, \quad (24)$$

$$313 \quad \mathbf{w} = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \Gamma. \quad (25)$$

314 By solving the coupled system of equations under the above boundary conditions for each of the
 315 three oscillatory tests, we can compute the averaged stress and strain tensor components over the
 316 REV, which allows us to calculate its effective anisotropic viscoelastic stiffness matrix. For the
 317 considered 2D case under plain strain conditions, the generalized anisotropic stress-strain
 318 relationship can be expressed as (Rubino et al., 2016)

$$319 \quad \begin{bmatrix} \langle \sigma_{11} \rangle \\ \langle \sigma_{22} \rangle \\ \langle \sigma_{12} \rangle \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{16} \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{26} \\ C_{16} & C_{26} & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \langle \varepsilon_{11} \rangle \\ \langle \varepsilon_{22} \rangle \\ \langle \varepsilon_{12} \rangle \end{bmatrix}, \quad (26)$$

320 where $\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle$ and $\langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle$ denote the volume averages of the stress and strain components, and \mathbf{C} is a
 321 complex-valued and frequency-dependent stiffness matrix. Unlike in Rubino et al. (2016), who
 322 employed a fully poroelastic framework, we are dealing with the coupled fluid-poroelastic problem
 323 and, thus, it is important to define the averaged stress and strain components that need to be used
 324 in equation (26). The averaged stress components can be expressed as

$$325 \quad \langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle = \frac{1}{S} \left(\int_{\Omega_p} T_{ij} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega_f} \sigma_{ij}^f d\Omega \right), \quad (27)$$

326 where S is the area of the REV. With respect to the averaged strain over the sample, the context of
 327 this work highlights that the contribution of the poroelastic regions to this quantity is not obvious.
 328 In previous works performed in a fully poroelastic context, $\langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle$ was simply the spatial average of
 329 Biot's definition of solid strain component E_{ij} (e.g., Rubino et al., 2016). However, this strain
 330 tensor contains only information on the displacement of the solid phase. Recall that even though
 331 the behavior of the sample in response to a relaxation test is obtained in the context of
 332 poroelasticity, the interpretation of the results is made in a viscoelastic context and, then, there is
 333 no clear reason as to why the deformation should be quantified using Biot's definition of solid
 334 strain. Indeed, it seems to be more appropriate to use an average displacement field \mathbf{u}_{pm} to
 335 approximate the deformation of the pore fluid-solid matrix system, that is,

$$336 \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{pm} = \frac{1}{2} \left[(\nabla \mathbf{u}_{pm}) + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_{pm})^T \right], \quad (28)$$

337 where $\mathbf{u}_{pm} = (1 - \phi)\mathbf{u} + \phi\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{w}$. Again, it is noted that the approximation is accurate as
 338 long as the deformation of the medium due to the passing of seismic waves is sufficiently small. Based
 339 on this approximation, the average strain of the sample can be expressed as

$$340 \quad \langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle = \frac{1}{S} \left(\int_{\Omega_p} \varepsilon_{ij}^{pm} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega_f} E_{ij}^f d\Omega \right). \quad (29)$$

341 Note that this approximation of strain is only used to estimate the overall averaged strain in the
 342 sample. However, we remark the following important aspects for this approximation. First, this
 343 new approximation of averaged strain accounting for the contribution of both solid and fluid
 344 phases in the poroelastic domain is reconcilable with the definition of the averaged stress in
 345 equation (27), where the total stress, rather than the solid stress, components T_{ij} are used for the
 346 poroelastic domain. In addition, the approximation in equations (28) and (29) is compatible with
 347 the interface conditions (equations (10) and (11)) imposed on the displacement fields at the contact
 348 between the porous background and the fluid inclusions and, thus, the resulting average strain $\langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle$
 349 equals the values computed using the displacements imposed at the outer boundaries of the sample,
 350 as expected and demonstrated in Appendix A. Moreover, this new approximation of strain is
 351 compatible with energetic considerations in the original heterogeneous, porous material. To
 352 support this, we introduce an independent energy-based approach (Solazzi et al., 2016) in section
 353 2.3, which calculates seismic attenuation using the Biot's (1962) definitions of dissipation power

354 and strain energy, but not using the dynamic-equivalent viscoelastic medium assumption. Note
 355 that in Biot's (1962) definition of strain energy, the contribution of the pore-fluid pressure is also
 356 included. For the considered coupled NS-Biot problem, this new approximation of equivalent
 357 strain, as opposed to Biot's (1962) definition of solid strain, provides results that are consistent
 358 with those using the independent energy-based approach (Appendix B). Finally, it should be noted
 359 that, in a purely poroelastic context and due to the periodicity usually imposed on the fluid flow at
 360 opposite boundaries of the sample, Biot's (1962) definition of strain E_{ij} (equation (3)) and that
 361 proposed in this work (equation (28)) provide the same averaged strain and, thus, the same
 362 effective seismic characteristics (Appendix B).

363
 364 The relationship established by equation (26) holds for the three oscillatory relaxation tests applied.
 365 This implies that we have nine equations and six unknowns (C_{ij} , with $i \leq j$). Following Rubino et
 366 al. (2016), we obtain the components of the effective stiffness matrix \mathbf{C} through a least-squares
 367 procedure. Once these elements have been retrieved, it is possible to compute the effective
 368 complex-valued as well as frequency- and angle-dependent wavenumber k_{qP} and k_{qS} for quasi- P -
 369 (qP) and quasi- S -waves (qS) (Rubino et al., 2016). The corresponding phase velocity and inverse
 370 quality factor as functions of frequency and incidence angle θ can be calculated using

$$371 \quad V_{qP,qS}(\omega, \theta) = \frac{\omega}{\mathcal{R}(k_{qP,qS}(\omega, \theta))}, \quad (30)$$

$$372 \quad \frac{1}{Q_{qP,qS}(\omega, \theta)} = -\frac{\mathcal{I}(k_{qP,qS}(\omega, \theta)^2)}{\mathcal{R}(k_{qP,qS}(\omega, \theta)^2)}, \quad (31)$$

373 where \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{I} refer to the real and imaginary parts, respectively.

374 2.3 Local Energy Dissipation

375 When studying seismic attenuation mechanisms, it is, in some cases, necessary to identify where,
 376 at a given frequency, the energy dissipation is taking place inside the probed sample. Following
 377 Solazzi et al. (2016), we therefore quantify the local contribution to the inverse quality factor,
 378 which is also referred to as the inverse quality factor density. For this, we first define several
 379 frequency-dependent functions. In the fluid domain Ω_f , the local dissipation power averaged over
 380 one wave cycle for a considered computational cell Δ_n of area δ_n^2 is given by (Lissa et al., 2020)

$$\langle \Delta \mathcal{P}^f(\omega)_n \rangle = 2\mu_f \omega^2 \mathcal{R} \left[\left(E_{11}^f E_{11}^{f*} + E_{22}^f E_{22}^{f*} + E_{12}^f E_{12}^{f*} \right) - \frac{1}{3} \left(E_{11}^f + E_{22}^f \right) \left(E_{11}^{f*} + E_{22}^{f*} \right) \right] \delta_n^2, \quad (32)$$

where the superscripts f and the asterisk (*) denote the fluid domain and the complex conjugate, respectively. In the poroelastic domain Ω_p , the local dissipation power in a cell Δ_m of the domain responds to (Rubino et al., 2016; Solazzi et al., 2016)

$$\langle \Delta \mathcal{P}^p(\omega)_m \rangle = \frac{\omega^2}{2} \left(\frac{\eta}{\kappa} \|\mathbf{w}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})\|^2 \right)_m \delta_m^2, \quad (33)$$

where the superscript p refers to the poroelastic domain Ω_p . In addition, the total strain energy function $\langle \mathcal{W}(\omega) \rangle$ of the REV is

$$\langle \mathcal{W}(\omega) \rangle = \sum_n \langle \mathcal{W}^f(\omega)_n \rangle + \sum_m \langle \mathcal{W}^p(\omega)_m \rangle, \quad (34)$$

where $\langle \mathcal{W}^f(\omega)_n \rangle$ and $\langle \mathcal{W}^p(\omega)_m \rangle$ are the strain energy functions for the fluid domain Ω_f and for the poroelastic domain Ω_p , respectively. They can be calculated using (Biot, 1962; Lissa et al., 2020; Rubino et al., 2016; Solazzi et al., 2016)

$$\langle \mathcal{W}^f(\omega)_n \rangle = \frac{1}{4} \mathcal{R}(\sigma_{11}^f E_{11}^{f*} + \sigma_{22}^f E_{22}^{f*} + 2\sigma_{12}^f E_{12}^{f*})_n \delta_n^2, \quad (35)$$

$$\langle \mathcal{W}^p(\omega)_m \rangle = \frac{1}{4} \mathcal{R}[(T_{11} E_{11}^* + T_{22} E_{22}^* + 2T_{12} E_{12}^*) + P_f \zeta^*]_m \delta_m^2. \quad (36)$$

Note that, in equation (36), the contribution of the pore fluid pressure to the strain energy is considered. We can now define the inverse quality factor density in terms of average power dissipation density and strain energy functions as (Solazzi et al., 2016)

$$q^{-1}(\omega) = \frac{\langle \Delta \mathcal{P}(\omega) \rangle}{2\omega \delta^2 \langle \mathcal{W}(\omega) \rangle}, \quad (37)$$

which will be used to study the wave attenuation mechanism. The summation of inverse quality factor density in equation (37) over the entirety of the probed sample then results in the inverse quality factor at a given frequency

$$Q^{-1}(\omega) = \sum_{\Omega_p + \Omega_f} q^{-1}(\omega) \delta^2. \quad (38)$$

401

403 2.4 Numerical Implementation

404 In the preceding sections, we presented the set of equations that permit to describe a coupled fluid-
405 poroelastic model as well as three associated oscillatory relaxation tests to obtain the upscaled

406 response of the medium. To solve this set of equations, we employ the “mathematical module” in
407 the finite-element-based software COMSOL Multiphysics. We use unstructured triangular meshes,
408 which allow for an efficient discretization of narrow features, such as fractures or fluid channels.
409 For the fluid domains and in their vicinities, we employ sufficiently fine meshing to accurately
410 capture the FPD effect in and near the fluid-poroelastic interface. Moreover, we use quadratic
411 Lagrange shape functions for both solid and relative fluid displacement variables of Biot’s
412 equations in the poroelastic domain. For the NS equations, quadratic shape functions are used for
413 fluid displacement variables. The discretized problem is solved using the direct parallel solver
414 MUMPS in the frequency domain, which readily enables us to evaluate the velocity dispersion and
415 attenuation spectra of seismic waves in the probed medium.

416 **3 Results**

417 In this section, we verify the effectiveness of the proposed approach using two numerical examples.
418 First, we analyze two orthogonal fractures embedded in a poroelastic background. We assess the
419 correctness of the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach by comparing it with two widely
420 used numerical upscaling schemes. One is the purely poroelastic approach (Rubino et al., 2016),
421 in which both the background and fractures are characterized using the Biot’s equations. The other
422 is the coupled fluid-elastic approach (Quintal et al., 2019), where the fractures are similarly
423 characterized by the NS equations, while the dynamic behavior of the background is characterized
424 using the quasi-static elastic equations. Then, we compare the three approaches considering the
425 influence of material properties as well as fracture apertures. In the second example, we investigate
426 the seismic attenuation and velocity dispersion of a synthetic carbonate-type sample containing
427 mesoscopic vugs embedded in a microscopic porous matrix.

428 3.1 Comparison with Previous Approaches

429 We consider a square REV with a side length of 0.2 m (Figure 2a) that contains two interconnected
430 orthogonal fractures orientated along the vertical and horizontal axes. The poroelastic background
431 medium is characterized by physical properties representative of a stiff quartz sandstone. We
432 assume that both the background and the fractures are fully saturated with water. The
433 corresponding physical rock and fluid properties are summarized in Table 1 (Bourbié et al., 1987;
434 Rubino et al., 2016). A schematic view of the mesh employed in the finite element simulations is

435 provided in Figure 2b. The mesh is refined near the boundaries of the fractures to correctly
 436 represent FPD processes. Note that for the considered model, in both the purely poroelastic
 437 approach and the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach, two attenuation peaks are expected,
 438 which correspond to fracture-to-background (FB) FPD and fracture-to-fracture (FF) FPD (Rubino
 439 et al., 2013). However, the coupled fluid-elastic approach can only predict one attenuation peak
 440 associated with FF-FPD effect. For the attenuation peak due to FB-FPD, the characteristic
 441 frequency of the associated maximum attenuation is directly proportional to the background
 442 permeability, while, for the attenuation peak due to FF-FPD, the characteristic frequency is directly
 443 proportional to the fracture permeability and inversely proportional to the length of the fractures
 444 (Rubino et al., 2017).

445
 446 Figure 2. (a) Canonical fracture model and (b) its discretization.

447

448

Table 1. Physical properties of background rock and pore fluid.

Background rock	Value
Grain density ρ_s (kg/m ³)	2650
Grain bulk modulus K_s (GPa)	37
Porosity ϕ	0.04
Drained bulk modulus K_b (GPa)	26
Drained shear modulus μ_b (GPa)	31
Permeability $\kappa(D)$	0.01
Fluid phase	
Density ρ_f (kg/m ³)	1090

Bulk modulus K_f (GPa)	2.25
Viscosity η (Pa · s)	0.001

449

450 *3.1.1 Seismic Attenuation and Phase Velocity Dispersion*

451 To validate the newly proposed method for computing seismic attenuation and phase velocity
452 dispersion of porous rocks containing fluid-filled voids in the mesoscopic scale range, we compare
453 our results with those obtained using a purely poroelastic approach (Rubino et al., 2016) and also
454 with those using a coupled fluid-elastic approach (Quintal et al., 2019). For the coupled fluid-
455 elastic approach, the poroelastic background is approximated with an equivalent elastic solid, for
456 which the effective bulk K_e and shear moduli μ_e are calculated using the Gassmann's (1951)
457 equations: $K_e = K_b + \alpha^2 M$ and $\mu_e = \mu_b$. The effective density is obtained using $\rho_e = \rho_s(1 -$
458 $\phi) + \rho_f \phi$. On the other hand, when using the purely poroelastic approach to represent fluid-filled
459 voids, we need to determine the corresponding effective properties of the porous material
460 representing them. For example, the permeability of the fracture has to be specified, whereas in
461 the proposed approach, the permeability is controlled by the geometrical characteristics of the
462 corresponding voids. Using the coupled fluid-elastic approach, Quintal et al. (2019) already
463 showed that, if appropriate material properties are used for the fractures, the two solutions should
464 be identical, at least with regard to FF-FPD effects. For the comparison, we assume that, at the
465 grain level, the physical properties of the fractures in the fully poroelastic model are the same as
466 those of the embedding background. With respect to the dry frame properties, as we intend to
467 represent mesoscopic void inclusions in a poroelasticity framework, we use a porosity value $\phi =$
468 0.999, which in turn, implies very low values of bulk and shear moduli. To choose these values,
469 we have checked that when K_b and μ_b are reduced to values that are much lower than the fluid
470 bulk modulus, the results of the purely poroelastic approach converge to those provided by the
471 proposed coupled approach. However, we cannot further reduce these moduli, otherwise,
472 numerical instabilities can occur. Therefore, in our work, we use $K_b = \mu_b = 3 \times 10^5$ Pa. Given
473 that each fracture has a rectangular geometry, with a constant aperture of $h = 3 \times 10^{-4}$ m and a
474 length of 0.16 m, we estimate the permeability of the porous material representing the fractures
475 using the so-called cubic law $\kappa = h^2 / 12$ (e.g., Jaeger et al., 2007). In this context, it is important
476 to notice that for the model considered, the two attenuation peaks are clearly separated in the

477 frequency domain. This implies that near the characteristic frequency of the attenuation peak due
478 to the fracture-to-fracture FPD, the induced fluid flow is restricted within the fractures and fluid
479 flow between fractures and porous background is negligible. Therefore, the cubic law provides
480 accurate estimation of fracture permeability. Using these material properties, the velocity
481 dispersion and attenuation characteristics of both qP - and qS -waves are calculated using the three
482 approaches. In doing so, we consider propagation angles θ with respect to the vertical of 0° and
483 45° . The corresponding results are shown in Figure 3 for frequencies ranging from 1 to 10^7 Hz.

484

485 We first compare the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach and the purely poroelastic
486 approach. For $\theta = 0^\circ$, the qP -wave exhibits significant phase velocity dispersion (Figure 3a)
487 presenting two inflections associated with FB-FPD and FF-FPD. Correspondingly, the Q^{-1} -
488 spectra show two attenuation peaks (Figure 3b). For $\theta = 45^\circ$, we observe only one attenuation
489 peak of the qP -wave in the low-frequency range due to FB-FPD (Figure 3b). The attenuation peak
490 due to the FF-FPD is not present due to the symmetry of the fracture network since, in this case,
491 both horizontal and vertical fractures are compressed equally by the passing qP -wave and
492 experience a similar fluid pressure increase. For both propagation angles, the two approaches
493 provide quite consistent results, with the maximum relative differences of phase velocity for the
494 two methods being less than 0.2%. Figures 3c and 3d illustrate the corresponding behavior of the
495 qS -wave. This wave mode exhibits very little dispersion and attenuation for $\theta = 0^\circ$ due to the
496 intrinsic geometry of the system. However, for $\theta = 45^\circ$, the attenuation related to FB-FPD is
497 insignificant, while we observe rather pronounced attenuation due to FF-FPD. For the latter, the
498 fluid pressures in the two fractures have opposite signs because the deformation induced by the
499 qS -wave extensional in one of the fractures and compressional in the other. Therefore, the
500 corresponding pressure gradient becomes very large between the two fractures (Rubino et al.,
501 2017). Again, the results are in quite good agreement for the two approaches, and the maximum
502 relative difference of qS -wave velocity for the two approaches is less than 0.7%.

503

504 When the coupled fluid-elastic approach is used, we observe consistent results only in the high-
505 frequency range where FF-FPD controls the seismic attenuation and velocity dispersion. This
506 further supports the effectiveness of the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach. However,

507 as expected, no attenuation and velocity dispersion are observed in the low-frequency range, which
 508 is one of the intrinsic limitations of the coupled fluid-elastic approach.

509

510 In summary, the results obtained using the newly proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach to
 511 model seismic signatures of porous rocks containing mesoscopic fluid-saturated fractures shows
 512 good agreement with a fully poroelastic representation of the medium, provided that suitable
 513 poroelastic fracture properties are considered. This demonstrates the correctness of the proposed
 514 upscaling scheme for representing FPD between mesoscopic fluid-filled inclusions and the porous
 515 background as well as between the mesoscopic inclusions themselves. The comparison with the
 516 coupled fluid-elastic approach further supports the effectiveness of the proposed approach and
 517 highlights the contribution of this work.

518

519 Figure 3. Comparison of qP -wave (a) phase velocity and (b) inverse quality factor and qS -wave
 520 (c) phase velocity and (d) inverse quality factor as functions of frequency for propagation angle θ
 521 of 0° and 45° with respect to the vertical. The results correspond to the fracture model shown in
 522 Figure 2. The “coupled NS-Biot” results are obtained using the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic

523 approach; the “Pure Biot” results are obtained using the purely poroelastic approach (Rubino et al.,
 524 2016), where both the background and the fractures are characterized by the Biot’s poroelastic
 525 equations (Biot, 1941); the “coupled NS-Elastic” results are obtained using the coupled fluid-
 526 elastic approach (Quintal et al., 2019), where the fractures are characterized using the NS equations,
 527 while the background is fully elastic with effective material parameters obtained using the
 528 Gassmann’s (1951) equation.

529

530 *3.1.2 Influence of Fracture Compliance in Purely Poroelastic Approach*

531 As shown above, the proposed fluid-poroelastic approach to compute the seismic signatures of
 532 porous media containing mesoscopic fluid inclusions provides results that, in some cases, can also
 533 be obtained following a purely poroelastic approach by optimizing the material properties inside
 534 the fluid inclusions. As previously mentioned, this is due to the fact that Biot’s (1941) equations
 535 involve more parameters when representing fluid inclusions, which may lead to ambiguity in their
 536 identification from seismic data. In the following, we investigate the influence of the drained bulk
 537 and shear moduli which are needed in the purely poroelastic approach to model the mesoscopic
 538 fluid-filled fractures. To this end, we analyze the response obtained using the purely poroelastic
 539 approach by varying the drained bulk modulus K_b for the fractures, which is a parameter that is
 540 not present in the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach. In the simulations, the drained
 541 shear modulus μ_b is assumed to be equal to the drained bulk modulus K_b to facilitate the analysis.
 542 The remaining physical properties and geometrical parameters are identical to those employed in
 543 Section 3.1.1.

544

545 Figure 4 illustrates the spectra of phase velocity and inverse quality factor of the qP -wave for $\theta =$
 546 0° and of the qS -wave for $\theta = 45^\circ$. We notice that the choice of the drained bulk and shear moduli
 547 has indeed a significant impact on the results, which, in relative terms, is more pronounced for the
 548 qS -wave (Figure 4d). For relatively small values of these moduli, the phase velocity curves
 549 converge to the same results as those obtained using the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic
 550 approach (Figures 4a to 4d). However, when larger values of the drained bulk modulus are used,
 551 significant changes are observed in the low-frequency range. The optimal value for emulating the
 552 NS representation of the fractures is $K_b = \mu_b = 3 \times 10^5$ Pa. It should be noted that this optimized

553 value cannot be generalized for other scenarios, as it varies with the model geometry. Another
 554 observation regarding the attenuation spectra is that the peaks are shifted towards higher
 555 frequencies and their amplitude decreases when increasing the fracture drained bulk and shear
 556 moduli.

557
 558 Figure 4. Influence of drained bulk and shear moduli of the fractures in the purely poroelastic
 559 approach on the qP -wave (a) phase velocity and (b) inverse quality factor as functions of frequency
 560 for propagation angle $\theta = 0^\circ$. (c) Phase velocity and (d) inverse quality factor of the qS -wave for
 561 $\theta = 45^\circ$. For all the simulations, the model is the same as that in Figure 2 and we set $\mu_b = K_b$ for
 562 simplicity. In the purely poroelastic approach, the permeability in the fracture is calculated using
 563 the cubic law.

564
 565 For this comparison, we assume that the mesoscopic fractures are fully fluid-saturated. However,
 566 we note that, for heterogeneities of this kind containing porous infills, such as unconsolidated
 567 grains, the purely poroelastic approach remains a suitable option, because both the geometry of
 568 inclusions and the infill determine the hydromechanical properties of heterogeneous porous rocks.

569 *3.1.3 Fracture Asperities*

570 Natural fractures tend to exhibit complicated roughness along their walls, also known as asperities,
 571 which affect the FPD process and, thus, the hydraulic and mechanical properties of the fractured
 572 rock mass. For generic asperities, there is no analytical expression that can relate explicitly the
 573 permeability and the fracture aperture. Quintal et al. (2019) studied squirt flow effects in
 574 interconnected fractures with asperities and compared the coupled fluid-elastic approach with a
 575 purely poroelastic solution. However, they ignored the low-frequency peak associated with FB-
 576 FPD predicted by the Biot's (1941) poroelastic equations because the coupled fluid-elastic
 577 approach assumes no fluid exchange between the elastic background and the fracture fluid.
 578 Recently, Lissa et al. (2020) investigated squirt flow in more complicated fractures and arrived to
 579 the conclusion that seismic signatures are significantly influenced by the roughness of the crack
 580 walls. In this section, we revisit this problem and compare the three approaches for the full
 581 frequency range to analyze both FB- and FF-FPD effects.

582

583 To emulate asperities, we consider a fracture wall with a symmetrically constricted geometry.
 584 Apart from the asperities, the considered model is the same as that employed previously (Figure
 585 2, Table 1). The local variation of the aperture is governed by a sinusoidal function except for the
 586 intersection between the two fractures. A unit cell of the considered fracture wall is illustrated in
 587 Figure 5, with δ and λ denoting the amplitude and wavelength, respectively, of the sinusoidal
 588 function, and d the mean aperture. For all simulations, we use $d = 0.3$ mm, $\delta = 0.2$ mm and $\lambda =$
 589 0.8 mm, which results in a minimum and maximum aperture of $h_{min} = 0.1$ mm and $h_{max} =$
 590 0.5 mm, respectively.

591

592 Figure 5. Schematic illustration of a unit cell of the considered fracture wall characterized by
 593 harmonic asperities.

594

595 We consider qP - and qS -waves with propagation angles θ of 0° and 45° , respectively. Figure 6
596 shows the phase velocity and the inverse quality factor as functions of frequency for the three
597 approaches. Note that during the simulations, we keep the roughness of the fracture wall the same
598 (Figure 5), but for the purely poroelastic approach, we use two different effective apertures (h_{min}
599 and h_{max}) to estimate the fracture permeability using the cubic law. We can still observe two
600 distinct attenuation peaks in the attenuation spectrum of the qP -wave when using the coupled fluid-
601 poroelastic approach and purely poroelastic approach. Compared to the model with rectangular
602 fractures (Figure 2), the attenuation peaks are shifted to lower frequencies, this effect being more
603 pronounced for the high-frequency peak. For the first attenuation peak, the results of the proposed
604 coupled fluid-poroelastic approach and the purely poroelastic approach considering the fracture
605 asperities are almost identical (Figure 6). The characteristic frequency associated with the first
606 peak is mainly controlled by the background permeability. In this sense, this attenuation peak
607 related to FB-FPD is insensitive to the fracture permeability. Both the proposed coupled fluid-
608 poroelastic approach and the purely poroelastic approach therefore predict similar values of
609 seismic attenuation and velocity dispersion at the frequencies where the energy dissipation is
610 controlled by the FB-FPD mechanism. Again, this attenuation is not predicted by the coupled fluid-
611 elastic approach (Figure 6b). For the second attenuation peak, we see that the results of the
612 proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach and the coupled fluid-elastic approach predict
613 identical values for both qP - and qS -waves (Figures 6b and 6d). However, we observe some
614 obvious differences in the characteristic frequency for the coupled fluid-poroelastic approach and
615 the purely poroelastic approach, even though they provide similar magnitude of attenuation. The
616 characteristic frequency predicted by the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach and coupled
617 fluid-elastic approach is 2×10^4 Hz, while for the purely poroelastic approach we get 4×10^3 Hz
618 and $\sim 10^5$ Hz when the minimum and maximum apertures, respectively, are used to evaluate the
619 effective permeability. As this second attenuation peak is an effect of FF-FPD, its characteristic
620 frequency is influenced by the fracture permeability. Even for this simple scenario, the peak
621 frequency of the purely poroelastic model can vary by more than one order-of-magnitude because
622 of the uncertainty of equivalent aperture selection to determine the effective permeability. In
623 practice, fracture networks tend to exhibit much more complicated aperture variations and

624 orientations. This renders the determination of an effective permeability for each fracture largely
625 impossible, which, in turn, makes the use of the purely poroelastic approach impractical.

626

627 It is important to remark here that a similar model that considers the dynamic interaction between
628 a fluid medium and a porous background has been previously proposed by Vinci et al. (2014a).
629 The authors use a 1D solution of the NS equations for laminar flow to characterize the dynamic
630 aspect within a fracture. Their approach is, however, incapable of dealing with fracture surfaces
631 exhibiting asperities or multiple intersecting fractures due to the inherent assumptions of axial
632 symmetry and the validity of the cubic law. These limitations were alleviated in our work by
633 solving the quasi-static linearized NS equations (Landau & Lifshitz, 1959; Quintal et al., 2016).
634 As shown in Figure 6, the employment of cubic law to estimate fracture permeability results in
635 uncertainties and errors, while the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach naturally accounts
636 for the fracture permeability and provides reliable results. In Figures 3 and 6, we demonstrated the
637 correctness of the proposed approach using a model with two interconnected and orthogonal
638 fractures orientated in the vertical and horizontal directions. It is important to note that the
639 proposed approach can be readily applied to multiple intersecting fractures with arbitrary
640 inclination angles since the proposed scheme permits to calculate anisotropic characteristics of
641 both qP - and qS -waves.

642

643 We analyzed above the influence of fracture asperities on the fracture permeability based on the
644 fracture model given in Figure 5. However, it is important to mention that asperities could also
645 have a strong impact on fracture compliance. Indeed, the fracture contact area density and
646 distribution play a very important role in the stiffness of fractured rocks (Rubino et al., 2015; Lissa
647 et al., 2020). In this context, it is important to notice that changes in effective fluid pressure of
648 fractures may induce variation in contact density and distribution of asperities. When the pressure
649 inside the fracture is increased, for example, due to fluid injection, the fracture aperture will
650 increase and fractures will have only isolated regions of contact. Conversely, when the fluid
651 pressure inside the fracture is decreased, for example due to production, the fracture aperture will
652 decrease, and the contact area increases (Rubino et al., 2015). The change of contact areas has a
653 significant impact on fracture permeability and compliance, which will result in variations of
654 seismic attenuation as well as other seismic attributes. In the future, we intend to perform a

655 comprehensive analysis of fracture contact area effects on permeability and compliance and on the
 656 corresponding impact on WIFF in 3D configurations.

657

658

659 Figure 6. Comparison of qP -wave (a) phase velocity and (b) inverse quality factor as functions of
 660 frequency for $\theta = 0^\circ$, and qS -wave (c) phase velocity and (d) inverse quality factor for $\theta = 45^\circ$
 661 obtained using three different approaches for a model of intersecting perpendicular fractures
 662 (Figure 2) with symmetric harmonically constricted walls (Figure 5). The “NS-Biot” results
 663 correspond to the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach, “pure Biot” results to the purely
 664 poroelastic model (Rubino et al., 2016), and “NS-Elastic” to the coupled fluid-elastic approach
 665 (Quintal et al., 2019).

666

667 To corroborate the above analyses and to investigate the seismic attenuation mechanism, we
 668 calculate the inverse quality factor density corresponding to the frequency of the first and the
 669 second attenuation peaks in Figure 6b using the coupled fluid-poroelastic approach and the purely

670 poroelastic approach, respectively. Results for the first attenuation peak are illustrated in Figures
 671 7a and 7b using a logarithmic scale. The two approaches provide very similar energy dissipation
 672 distributions with strong energy dissipation occurring mainly in the poroelastic background, being
 673 more pronounced near the fracture walls and particularly in the vicinity of the fracture tips. The
 674 results in Figures 7c and 7d correspond to the characteristic frequency of the second peak. We
 675 depict the inverse quality factor density near the intersection area where the energy dissipation is
 676 most representative and pronounced. We see that, for both approaches, energy dissipation mainly
 677 takes place at the narrowest regions of the fractures, where fluid flow is enhanced due to fluid mass
 678 conservation and a change in fracture cross section, while it is almost negligible in the poroelastic
 679 background. For the coupled approach, we observe minimal energy dissipation at the center of the
 680 fracture, and the maximum values at the fracture walls, where fluid velocity reaches its lowest
 681 values due to viscous friction (Figure 7c). For the purely poroelastic approach, the energy
 682 dissipation is more uniform in the narrowest regions (Figure 7d). Analyses of this kind are of
 683 relevance for applications, in which the location of maximal fluid shearing is relevant, such as, for
 684 example, studies regarding the mobilization of colloids and particles in response to FPD (e.g.,
 685 Barbosa et al., 2019).

686

687 Figure 7. Distribution of inverse quality factor density for intersecting fractures with symmetric
688 harmonically constricted walls. (a) and (b) correspond to the frequency of the first attenuation peak
689 related to FB-FPD and (c) and (d) to that of the second attenuation peak related to FF-FPD shown
690 in Figure 6b. (a) and (c) are based on the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach, while (b)
691 and (d) are based on the purely poroelastic approach. Note that the top panel is displayed in a
692 logarithmic colorscale.

693 3.2 Application in a Vuggy Carbonate-type Sample

694 Porous and/or karstic carbonates play an important role in the oil and gas industry, accounting for
695 ~60% of the global reserves (e.g., Burchette, 2012, Agada et al., 2016). Furthermore, carbonate
696 aquifers provide drinking water to ~10% of the world's population (e.g., Goldscheider et al., 2020).
697 One of the major challenges when studying carbonates is the correct characterization of their
698 hydro-mechanical characteristics. In this sense, permeabilities of carbonates can vary several
699 orders-of-magnitude for the same porosity and the pore sizes tend to exhibit an extreme variability
700 ranging from the micro- all the way to the macroscale (e.g., Burchette, 2012). These distinctive
701 properties of carbonates were analyzed by Anselmetti et al. (1998), who explored the relations
702 between the local permeability and the associated size distributions of the pores, which were
703 constituted of both micro- and mesopores in the micro- and millimeter scale ranges, respectively.
704 Agersborg et al. (2009) showed that significant variations of the acoustic properties in carbonates
705 can be explained by the effects of dual porosity and pore pressure communication. In a more recent
706 work, Bailly et al. (2019) studied the elastic properties of carbonates based on a multiscale
707 geophysical dataset obtained through seismic refraction surveying as well as sonic and ultrasonic
708 measurements on outcrop samples. Their results indicate that mesoscale fluid inclusions have a
709 considerable impact on P -wave velocities. However, as far as we know, there are, as of yet, no
710 works assessing the effective seismic characteristics of carbonates accounting for complex fluid-
711 filled mesopores in combination with a poroelastic background. In the following, we seek to
712 overcome this limitation by applying the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic upscaling scheme to
713 a pertinent synthetic sample.

714

715 Inspired by the optical thin-section images of Anselmetti et al. (1998), we emulate the mesoscale
716 voids of a synthetic carbonate-type sample using a binarized stochastic model based on a Gaussian

717 spectral density function. The considered REV is illustrated in Figure 8. The side length of the
 718 sample is 0.18 m. The model contains a number of mesoscale voids (green regions) embedded in
 719 a porous background (white region). The latter is constituted of a calcite matrix containing
 720 micropores and, as such, is represented by the Biot's (1941) equations. The characteristic size of
 721 the mesopores varies from hundreds of micrometers to several centimeters and they present a
 722 horizontal-to-vertical aspect ratio of 4. Within these mesopores, the NS equations are used to
 723 describe the motion of the saturating fluid.

724
 725 Figure 8. Synthetic carbonate-type sample containing mesoscale fluid-saturated voids (green)
 726 embedded in a poroelastic background (white).

727
 728 For computing the effective seismic characteristics of this medium, we consider for the porous
 729 background that, at the grain scale, the elastic properties are those of pure calcite: $K_s = K_{calcite} =$
 730 71 GPa , $\mu_s = \mu_{calcite} = 30 \text{ GPa}$, and $\rho_s = \rho_{calcite} = 2710 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (Mavko et al., 2009). For the
 731 porous matrix, we use typical values of microporosities and micropermeabilities of carbonate
 732 samples measured by Anselmetti et al. (1998): $\phi = 0.12$ and $\kappa = 0.1 \text{ mD}$. The drained bulk and
 733 shear moduli are calculated employing the asymptotic expressions proposed by David and
 734 Zimmerman (2011), where the medium is assumed to contain dry circular pores. Using the values
 735 of grain moduli and the porosity, we get $K_b = 50.41 \text{ GPa}$ and $\mu_b = 23.54 \text{ GPa}$. We assume that
 736 both the micropores and mesopores are fully saturated with water, the physical properties of which
 737 are summarized in Table 1. The model is discretized using unstructured triangular meshes, which
 738 are locally refined in the vicinity of the boundary of the fluid-filled voids.

739

740 The seismic velocity dispersion and attenuation spectra of the qP - and qS -waves are shown in
 741 Figure 9 for a range of incidence angles θ . For the qP -wave, we observe that, both the phase
 742 velocity and the inverse quality factor are dependent on the frequency and on the propagation angle
 743 (Figures 9a and 9b). In particular, the qP -wave shows very significant dispersion for vertical
 744 propagation. At the peak frequency $f = 7.5$ Hz, the Q_p -values are ~ 40 . With increasing
 745 propagation angle, dispersion and attenuation decrease very rapidly and, for the horizontal
 746 propagation, become almost insignificant. Another observation is the high degree of qP -wave
 747 velocity anisotropy, which is more pronounced at low frequencies. The results of the qS -wave are
 748 depicted in Figures 9c and 9d. Again, we observe a distinct attenuation peak, for which the peak
 749 frequency is the same as that for the qP -wave. However, the dispersion of the qS -wave is weaker.
 750 In the case of horizontal and vertical propagation, the dispersion and attenuation of the qS -wave
 751 are largely insignificant. The most pronounced velocity dispersion and attenuation occur for a
 752 propagation angle of $\theta = 45^\circ$. The anisotropy associated with the propagation of the qS -wave is
 753 very small compared to that of the qP -wave.

754

755

756 Figure 9. qP -wave (a) phase velocity and (b) inverse quality factor and qS -wave (c) phase velocity
 757 and (d) inverse quality factor as functions of frequency and propagation angle θ .

758

759 To understand the underlying mechanism of the observed seismic attenuation and velocity
 760 dispersion, we study the inverse quality factor density and the fluid pressure distributions in
 761 response to the oscillatory relaxation tests. For the considered carbonate sample, the coefficients
 762 C_{16} and C_{26} are much smaller than other components in the stiffness matrix (not shown here),
 763 which implies that it can be considered as a transversely isotropic medium. In this case, the vertical
 764 and horizontal compressibility tests can be associated with the qP -wave propagating with an angle
 765 θ of 0° and 90° , and the shear test corresponds to the qS -wave propagation in the vertical direction.
 766 Figure 10 illustrates the inverse quality factor density of both qP - and qS -waves at the frequency
 767 of the attenuation peak. In each case, we observe that the dissipation occurs mainly in the
 768 poroelastic background. For qP -wave propagation with $\theta = 90^\circ$ (Figure 10b), the spatial
 769 attenuation pattern is similar to that of $\theta = 0^\circ$ (Figure 10a), but the regions with significant energy
 770 dissipation are much smaller and are associated with lower values. This explains the reduction of
 771 attenuation observed in Figure 9 for $\theta = 90^\circ$. As expected, small values of quality factor density
 772 are also observed when the qS -wave propagates vertically (Figure 10c). For all these results, the
 773 attenuation is dominated by FPD between the larger mesopores and the embedding microporous
 774 background, while the contribution of the smaller voids is of subordinate importance. This is due
 775 to the fact that the compliance of larger voids is significantly higher than that of smaller ones.

776

777 Figure 10. Distribution of the inverse quality factor density for the synthetic carbonate-type rock
 778 shown in Figure 8 at the frequency of the attenuation peak (Figures 9b and 9d). Results of the qP -
 779 wave propagation in (a) vertical direction, (b) horizontal direction; and (c) result of the qS -wave
 780 propagation in vertical direction.

781

782 To further explore the role played by the different pore sizes on the seismic response, we illustrate
783 in Figure 11 the corresponding fluid pressure distributions. It is observed that, where energy
784 dissipation is strong (Figure 10), there are relatively obvious pressure surges inside the
785 corresponding fluid inclusions. Recall that the fluid inclusions and the poroelastic background are
786 hydraulically connected. The seismic wave motion causes some of the mesoscopic voids to be
787 strongly deformed due to their large compliances, which, in turn, increases the fluid pressure in
788 the corresponding voids. Due to the thus arising pressure disequilibrium, fluid pressure
789 communication takes place locally between the mesoscopic voids and the embedding microporous
790 background. The diffusion of the fluid pressure in the poroelastic background leads to the observed
791 local energy dissipation and resulting seismic attenuation (Figures 9 and 10). Since the
792 compliances of fluid-filled inclusions are related to their elongated shapes and their sizes, this leads
793 to the anisotropic characteristics of seismic velocity dispersion and attenuation depicted in Figure
794 9.

795

796 Based on the visualizations of the prevailing energy dissipation process in Figures 10 and 11, our
797 results confirm the observation of Agersborg et al. (2009) that FB-FPD is responsible for the
798 seismic attenuation in carbonate rocks. The characteristic frequency of this manifestation is mainly
799 controlled by the permeability of the embedding porous medium and is expected to be influenced
800 by the geometry and distribution of mesoscopic voids. Due to the preferential orientation of the
801 inclusions, our results show no significant evidence of FPD within the limited number of connected
802 voids. For mesopore networks that are more complex in terms of orientation and interconnectivity,
803 the results might, however, differ in this regard. In the future, we will extend the numerical scheme
804 to the 3D case and will explore the response of more realistic mesopore and/or fracture networks.
805 It should also be noted that seismic attenuation in real carbonate rocks is a multiscale problem. In
806 this work, we focused on mesoscopic FPD effects and, hence, ignored scattering effects and other
807 dissipation mechanisms prevailing at high frequencies, such as attenuation due to macroscopic
808 global flow and microscopic squirt flow.

809
 810 Figure 11. Distribution of fluid pressure at the frequency of the attenuation peak (Figure 9) in the
 811 poroelastic background and in the mesoscale voids for qP -wave propagation in the (a) vertical
 812 direction and (b) horizontal direction. (c) Corresponding results for qS -wave propagation in the
 813 vertical direction.

814

815 4 Discussion

816 While the numerical results demonstrate the robustness and flexibility of the proposed numerical
 817 upscaling procedure to calculate seismic attenuation of porous rocks containing mesoscopic fluid
 818 inclusions, assumptions upon which the proposed approach is based merit some consideration.
 819 First, we consider that seismic attenuation is controlled by FPD at the mesoscopic scale, and other
 820 factors that potentially affect the seismic response at higher frequencies, such as squirt flow (e. g.,
 821 Gueguen & Sarout, 2011), Biot's global flow and scattering, are neglected. This is reasonable in
 822 the seismic exploration frequency band for the considered characteristic sizes of the inclusions.
 823 We also assumed that the mesoscopic voids and the embedding porous background are fully
 824 saturated with a unique fluid. The partially saturated case warrants further exploration, as the
 825 presence of a second fluid phase may change the characteristics of the FPD processes (Solazzi et
 826 al, 2021). Moreover, we considered open-pore interface conditions between the fluid inclusions
 827 and embedding porous background. Future work should further explore the influence of sealed-
 828 pore and partially open-pore interface conditions. In addition, we assumed that there is no slip at

829 the interface in the tangential direction between the fluid inclusions and porous background. This
830 is reasonable in the framework of small deformation assumed throughout this work.

831

832 There are also some intrinsic limitations in the proposed approach. For example, the overall
833 procedure is conceived for heterogeneities having sizes at the mesoscopic scale range and, hence,
834 not appropriate for assessing physical processes occurring at the microscopic scale. In addition,
835 poroelasticity belongs to the macroscopic framework of continuum mechanics (Fortin & Guéguen,
836 2021), whereas the Navier-Stokes equation determines the behavior of fluids at microscopic scale.
837 In this work, we attempted to couple these two different systems using appropriate interface
838 conditions. To achieve this, at the interface, the microscopic details should be neglected due to the
839 employment of Biot's equations. For the region governed by the Navier-Stokes equation, once the
840 microscopic details of the interface are neglected, the microscopic characteristics of the fluid can
841 be upscaled to the macroscopic and mesoscopic scales (Zampogna et al., 2019). This, in turn,
842 allows the coupling between the fluid region and the adjacent poroelastic system. In this context,
843 it is important to remark that the coupling between a porous medium and a fluid is very common
844 and has wide applications in many fields, such as, for example, geophysics (e. g., Lefeuvre-
845 Mesgouez et al., 2012), fluid mechanics (e. g., Badia et al., 2009) and civil engineering (e. g.,
846 Vuong et al., 2015). The good agreement of the numerical results obtained using different
847 upscaling approaches supports the correctness of our methodology.

848

849 **5 Conclusions**

850 We introduced a novel fluid-poroelastic model and an associate numerical upscaling procedure to
851 the determine the effective seismic characteristics of porous rocks containing mesoscopic fluid-
852 filled voids. The model couples the quasi-static NS equations describing the fluid-filled
853 heterogeneities and Biot's consolidation equations for the poroelastic background through
854 appropriate interface conditions. Numerical upscaling is performed through three numerical
855 oscillatory relaxation tests on representative 2D samples characterized by the proposed hybrid
856 fluid-poroelastic model. The averaged stress and strain inferred from the three tests can be used to
857 compute the complex-valued and frequency-dependent stiffness matrix of an effective viscoelastic

858 medium, which then enables us to calculate the equivalent seismic attenuation and phase velocity
859 spectra. In this context, we also introduce the inverse quality factor density to explore the
860 prevailing attenuation mechanisms in more detail.

861
862 We first compare the proposed approach to the purely poroelastic approach as well as the coupled
863 fluid-elastic approach based on a well-known benchmark-type fracture model. We observed that
864 the proposed approach and purely poroelastic approach provide similar results of inverse quality
865 factors and phase velocities provided that the material properties are optimized when representing
866 voids as poroelastic features. Accounting for the effects of asperities along the fracture walls
867 reveals that the two approaches provide consistent results with regard to seismic attenuation due
868 to FB-FPD. Conversely, the results related to FF-FPD significantly differ in terms of the
869 characteristic frequencies associated with the corresponding attenuation peaks, while the
870 magnitudes are comparable. This frequency shift is related to the estimation of the effective
871 permeability of the fracture, which is a key parameter for the purely poroelastic approach.
872 Conversely, the permeability is naturally accounted for through the model geometry in the
873 proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach. We also observe that the proposed approach and the
874 coupled fluid-elastic approach predict similar seismic attenuation due to FF-FPD, which further
875 supports the correctness of the proposed approach. However, the limitation of the coupled fluid-
876 elastic approach is that it assumes a fully elastic background and, hence, does not account for FB-
877 FPD. Finally, we explore the seismic characteristics of a synthetic vuggy carbonate-type rock
878 sample using the proposed approach. We observe significant velocity dispersion and attenuation
879 of qP - and qS -waves in the seismic frequency band, which, based on the spatial distributions of
880 the inverse quality factor density and the fluid pressure, can be attributed to fluid pressure
881 communication between the mesoscopic vugs and microscopic pores of the embedding
882 background.

883

884

885 **Appendix A. Analysis of the New Approximation of Effective Strain for Poroelastic Media**

886

887 In section 2.2, in the framework of the proposed procedure of numerical upscaling, it is necessary
888 to compute the averaged strains over the sample. Since the interpretation is made in a viscoelastic

889 context, the final values of averaged strain should be consistent with those obtained using the
 890 imposed BCs for our problem. In the following, we analyze this consistency for the new
 891 approximation of effective poroelastic strains proposed in equation (28). To this end, we consider
 892 two oscillatory relaxation tests as illustrated in Figure A1 for the coupled problem, where a fluid
 893 inclusion Ω_f is embedded in the porous background Ω_p .

894
 895 Figure A1. Sketch of 2D coupled fluid-poroelastic problem to analyze the volume average of (a)
 896 diagonal components and (b) non-diagonal component of strain.

897

898 1. Diagonal components of averaged strain

899 For the analysis of the diagonal components of averaged strain, we consider the vertical
 900 compressibility relaxation test shown in Figure A1(a). We calculate the volume average of the
 901 vertical component of strain over the coupled medium as

$$904 \quad \langle \epsilon_{22} \rangle = \frac{1}{L_x L_y} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_x} \epsilon_{22}(x, y) dx dy = \frac{1}{L_x L_y} \left[\int_{\Omega_p} \epsilon_{22}^{pm}(x, y) dV + \int_{\Omega_f} E_{22}^f(x, y) dV \right]. \quad (A1)$$

902 For the poroelastic medium, we consider the new approximation of effective strain proposed in
 903 equation (28), for which the vertical component takes the form

$$905 \quad \epsilon_{22}^{pm}(x, y) = \frac{\partial(u_2 + w_2)}{\partial y}, \quad (A2)$$

906 where u_i is the i th component of solid displacement, and w_i is the i th component of fluid
 907 displacement relative to the solid matrix. For the fluid inclusion, the vertical component of strain
 908 is given by equation (8) as

$$909 \quad E_{22}^f(x, y) = \frac{\partial u_2^f}{\partial y}, \quad (A3)$$

910 where u_i^f is the i th component of fluid displacement.

911 For mathematical simplicity, we define two functions as

$$912 \quad \mathbf{P}(x, y) = (0, u_2(x, y) + w_2(x, y)), \quad \mathbf{Q}(x, y) = (0, u_2^f(x, y)). \quad (A4)$$

913 Thus, we have

$$914 \quad \int_{\Omega_p} \varepsilon_{22}^{pm}(x, y) dV = \int_{\Omega_p} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{P}(x, y) dV, \quad \int_{\Omega_f} E_{22}^f(x, y) dV = \int_{\Omega_f} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{Q}(x, y) dV. \quad (A5)$$

915 By applying the divergence theorem, we get

$$916 \quad \int_{\Omega_p} \varepsilon_{22}^{pm}(x, y) dV = \int_{\Gamma_p} \mathbf{P}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n} ds, \quad \int_{\Omega_f} E_{22}^f(x, y) dV = \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{Q}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n}' ds. \quad (A6)$$

917 where \mathbf{n} is the outward-directed unit normal vector on the boundaries Γ_p of the porous domain,
 918 and Γ_{pf} is a closed trajectory defining the interface of the fluid and porous domains. Note that at
 919 the interface, we have $\mathbf{n} = -\mathbf{n}'$.

920 Operating with equation (A6), we obtain

$$921 \quad \int_{\Omega_p} \varepsilon_{22}^{pm}(x, y) dV = \int_0^{L_x} \mathbf{P}(x, 0) \cdot (0, -1) dx + \int_0^{L_y} \mathbf{P}(L_x, y) \cdot (1, 0) dy + \int_0^{L_x} \mathbf{P}(x, L_y) \cdot (0, 1) dx \\
 + \int_0^{L_y} \mathbf{P}(0, y) \cdot (-1, 0) dy + \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{P}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n} ds. \quad (A7)$$

922 From equation (A4), we have

$$923 \quad \mathbf{P}(L_x, y) \cdot (1, 0) = [0, u_2(L_x, y) + w_2(L_x, y)] \cdot (1, 0) = 0, \quad (A8)$$

$$924 \quad \mathbf{P}(0, y) \cdot (-1, 0) = [0, u_2(0, y) + w_2(0, y)] \cdot (-1, 0) = 0. \quad (A9)$$

925 Considering the imposed BCs on the bottom edge of the REV (equations (14) and (17)), that is,
 926 $u_2(x, 0) = \Delta u$ and $w_2(x, 0) = 0$, we have

$$927 \quad \int_0^{L_x} \mathbf{P}(x, 0) \cdot (0, -1) dx = -\Delta u \cdot L_x. \quad (A10)$$

928 On the top edge of the REV, we impose $u_2(x, L_y) = -\Delta u$ and $w_2(x, L_y) = 0$ (equations (14) and
 929 (17)), so we have

$$930 \quad \int_0^{L_x} \mathbf{P}(x, L_y) \cdot (0, 1) dx = -\Delta u \cdot L_x. \quad (A11)$$

931 Substituting equations (A8) to (A11) into equation (A7), we get

$$932 \quad \int_{\Omega_p} \epsilon_{22}^{pm}(x, y) dV = -2\Delta u \cdot L_x + \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{P}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n} ds. \quad (A12)$$

933 For equation (A6), we also have

$$934 \quad \int_{\Omega_f} E_{22}^f(x, y) dV = \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{Q}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n}' ds = - \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{Q}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n} ds. \quad (A13)$$

935 Substituting equations (A12) and (A13) into equation (A1) yields

$$936 \quad \langle \epsilon_{22} \rangle = \frac{-2\Delta u}{L_y} + \frac{1}{L_x L_y} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} [\mathbf{P}(x, y) - \mathbf{Q}(x, y)] \cdot \mathbf{n} ds. \quad (A14)$$

937 Recalling the interface conditions (equations (10) and (11)), we have $\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{u}^f$ at all points of
 938 Γ_{pf} , which means that

$$939 \quad \frac{1}{L_x L_y} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} [\mathbf{P}(x, y) - \mathbf{Q}(x, y)] \cdot \mathbf{n} ds = 0. \quad (A15)$$

940 The volume average of strain is finally obtained as

$$941 \quad \langle \epsilon_{22} \rangle = \frac{-2\Delta u}{L_y}, \quad (A16)$$

942 which is consistent with the value that we obtain from the imposed BCs.

943

944 It is important to remark here that, if the Biot's definition of solid strain is used, we can define the
 945 function

$$946 \quad \mathbf{P}'(x, y) = (0, u_2). \quad (A17)$$

947 Following a similar derivation, the volume average of strain is obtained

$$948 \quad \langle \epsilon_{22} \rangle = \frac{-2\Delta u}{L_y} + \frac{1}{L_x L_y} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} [\mathbf{P}'(x, y) - \mathbf{Q}(x, y)] \cdot \mathbf{n} ds. \quad (A18)$$

949 The second term on the right-hand side of the equation corresponds to a residual due to the
 950 incorrect representation of the displacement field of the porous region using a single-phase
 951 medium in a viscoelastic context.

952

953 We can draw similar conclusions for $\langle \epsilon_{11} \rangle$ if a horizontal compressibility relaxation test is
 954 considered, which is omitted here for brevity.

955

956 2. Non-diagonal components of averaged strain

957 For the analysis of the non-diagonal components of strain, we consider the shear relaxation test
 958 illustrated in Figure A1(b). The volume average of the shear strain over the REV can be computed
 959 as

$$960 \quad \langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle = \frac{1}{L_x L_y} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_x} \epsilon_{12}(x, y) dx dy = \frac{1}{L_x L_y} \left[\int_{\Omega_p} \epsilon_{12}^{pm}(x, y) dV + \int_{\Omega_f} E_{12}^f(x, y) dV \right], \quad (\text{A19})$$

961 where we consider the new approximation of strain $\epsilon_{12}^{pm}(x, y)$ defined in equation (28) for the
 962 poroelastic medium. Thus, we have

$$963 \quad \int_{\Omega_p} \epsilon_{12}^{pm}(x, y) dV = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_p} \left[\frac{\partial(u_1 + w_1)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(u_2 + w_2)}{\partial x} \right] dV, \quad (\text{A20})$$

964 and using the definition in equation (8) for the fluid inclusion, we get

$$965 \quad \int_{\Omega_f} E_{12}^f(x, y) dV = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_f} \left[\frac{\partial u_1^f}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_2^f}{\partial x} \right] dV. \quad (\text{A21})$$

966 We define the following functions

$$967 \quad \mathbf{F}(x, y) = (u_2 + w_2, u_1 + w_1), \quad \mathbf{G}(x, y) = (u_2^f, u_1^f). \quad (\text{A22})$$

968 Combining equations (A19) to (A22) and using the divergence theorem, we have

$$969 \quad \langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle = \frac{1}{L_x L_y} \left[\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma_p} \mathbf{F}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n} ds + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{G}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n}' ds \right]. \quad (\text{A23})$$

970 For the first term on the right-hand side of equation (A23), we have

$$971 \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma_p} \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{n} ds &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_x} \mathbf{F}(x, 0) \cdot (0, -1) dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_y} \mathbf{F}(L_x, y) \cdot (1, 0) dy + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_x} \mathbf{F}(x, L_y) \cdot (0, 1) dx \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_y} \mathbf{F}(0, y) \cdot (-1, 0) dy + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{F}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n} ds. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A24})$$

972 Considering the imposed BCs on the bottom edge of the REV (equations (22) and (25)), that is,
 973 $u_1(x, 0) = -\Delta u$ and $w_1(x, 0) = 0$, we get

$$974 \quad \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_x} \mathbf{F}(x, 0) \cdot (0, -1) dx = \frac{1}{2} \Delta u \cdot L_x. \quad (\text{A25})$$

975 For the BCs on the right edge of the REV (equations (23) and (25)), we impose $u_2(L_x, y) = 0$ and
 976 $w_2(L_x, y) = 0$. We obtain

$$977 \quad \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_y} \mathbf{F}(L_x, y) \cdot (1, 0) dy = 0. \quad (\text{A26})$$

978 On the top edge of the REV (equations (22) and (25)), we impose $u_1(x, L_y) = \Delta u$ and
 979 $w_1(x, L_y) = 0$. We thus have

$$980 \quad \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_x} \mathbf{F}(x, L_y) \cdot (0, 1) dx = \frac{1}{2} \Delta u \cdot L_x. \quad (\text{A27})$$

981 Finally, on the left edge of the REV (equations (23) and (25)), we impose $u_2(0, y) = 0$ and
 982 $w_2(0, y) = 0$. Thus, we have

$$983 \quad \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_y} \mathbf{F}(0, y) \cdot (-1, 0) dy = 0. \quad (\text{A28})$$

984 Substituting equations (A25) to (A28) into equation (A24), we get

$$985 \quad \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma_p} \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{n} ds = \Delta u \cdot L_x + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{F}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n} ds. \quad (\text{A29})$$

986 For the second term on the right-hand side of the equation (A23), we have

$$987 \quad \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{G}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n}' ds = -\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} \mathbf{G}(x, y) \cdot \mathbf{n} ds. \quad (\text{A30})$$

988 Substituting equations (A29) and (A30) into equation (A23), we have

$$989 \quad \langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle = \frac{1}{L_y} \Delta u + \frac{1}{2L_x L_y} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} [\mathbf{F}(x, y) - \mathbf{G}(x, y)] \cdot \mathbf{n} ds. \quad (\text{A31})$$

990 Recalling the interface condition in equations (10) and (11), we have $\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{u}^f$ at all points of
 991 Γ_{pf} , which means that

$$992 \quad \frac{1}{2L_x L_y} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} [\mathbf{F}(x, y) - \mathbf{G}(x, y)] \cdot \mathbf{n} ds = 0. \quad (\text{A34})$$

993 Finally, we get

994
$$\langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle = \frac{\Delta u}{L_y}, \quad (\text{A35})$$

995 which is the same value as that obtained using the imposed displacement on the outer boundaries.

996

997 If the Biot's definition of solid strain is used instead, we define

998
$$\mathbf{F}'(x, y) = (u_2, u_1). \quad (\text{A36})$$

999 Following similar steps as before, we obtain

1000
$$\langle \epsilon_{12} \rangle = \frac{\Delta u}{L_y} + \frac{1}{2L_x L_y} \int_{\Gamma_{pf}} [\mathbf{F}'(x, y) - \mathbf{G}(x, y)] \cdot \mathbf{n} ds, \quad (\text{A37})$$

1001 where, on the right-hand side of the equation, the integral term is the residual due to an incorrect
 1002 representation of the displacement field of the porous region using a single-phase medium in a
 1003 viscoelastic context.

1004

1005 **Appendix B. Consistency of the New Approximation of Average Strain with the Energy-**
 1006 **based Approach**

1007 We consider the same model as presented in Figure 2, and calculate the inverse quality factor of
 1008 the qP -wave for a vertical direction of propagation. We compare the results obtained using the
 1009 proposed approach based on the dynamic-equivalent viscoelastic assumption with a reference
 1010 solution obtained using the energy-based approach (equation (38)). More specifically, when using
 1011 the former, we consider both Biot's definition of solid strain (defined in equation (3)) and the new
 1012 approximation of strain (equation (28)) for the porous domain to compute the volume average
 1013 strain of the sample. Results for the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach are depicted in
 1014 Figure B1(a). We see that the attenuation spectrum corresponding to the new approximation of
 1015 effective strain is in good agreement with that using the energy-based approach. However, when
 1016 Biot's definition of solid strain is considered, the attenuation is different from that of the energy-
 1017 based approach due to the incorrect estimation of the volume average strain of the sample. We also
 1018 show the results based on the purely poroelastic approach in Figure B1(b). In this case, we observe
 1019 that both the new approximation and Biot's definition of strain provide the same result as that
 1020 using the energy-based approach. This agreement is due to the periodicity imposed on the fluid
 1021 flow at opposite boundaries of the REV. Similar results were also observed for the qS -wave, which
 1022 are omitted here for brevity.

1023
 1024 Figure B1. Inverse quality factor of the qP -wave as a function of frequency for vertical propagation
 1025 obtained using (a) the proposed coupled fluid-poroelastic approach and (b) the purely poroelastic
 1026 approach. The results correspond to the model in Figure 2. For the inputs of the approach based
 1027 on the dynamic-equivalent viscoelastic assumption, “New approximation” refers to the estimation
 1028 of average strain in the poroelastic domain using equation (28), while “Biot’s definition” denotes
 1029 using the Biot’s definition of solid strain defined in equation (3).

1030

1031 **Data Availability Statement**

1032 Data sets are available online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5574304>).

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